

Asian Journal of Religious Studies

“The Lord is truly among us.”

July-August 2019

Vol 64/4

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Asian Journal for Religious Studies (AJRS) is a pastoral journal for Christian leaders. It is a bimonthly published from the Papal Seminary, Pune 411014. Inspiring and brief articles beneficial for Christian leaders are welcome.

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Printed at: Kunal Offset, Pune
Typeset at: Papal Seminary Centenary Computer Centre
Publisher: Kuruvilla Pandikattu, Papal Seminary

Subscriptions may be sent either by M.O. or D.D. If sent by cheque, please add Rs. 15 as bank commission. Annual Subscription Rate: Rs. 100 (in India); \$ 5 (in Asia); \$/Euro 12 (in Europe & America)

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ISSN 2249-1503

Editorial

A Message of Hope and Joy

The visit of Rev Fr Arturo Sosa, the Superior General of the Society of Jesus to Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune, campus on March 5-7, 2019 was truly a moment of grace for the whole campus. So this issue of our Journal is focused mostly on his visit.

Born on 12 November 1948, Arturo is the thirty-first and present Superior General of the Society of Jesus. He was elected Superior General by the Society's 36th General Congregation on 14 October 2016, succeeding Adolfo Nicolás. As a Venezuelan, he is the first person born in Latin America to lead the Jesuits.

On 14 October 2016, during the thirty-sixth General Congregation of the Society of Jesus, the assembly elected Sosa as the Order's thirty-first Superior General to succeed Adolfo Nicolás. He became the first Latin American to head the Jesuits. In his first address as Superior General, he said that Jesuits should look for "alternatives to overcome poverty, inequality and oppression" and also to collaborate with others "inside and outside the Church".

In 2017, in a visit to the Jesuit mission in Cambodia, Sosa met with a group of Buddhist monks in the Buddhist-majority country. In 2018, commenting on the Fifteenth Ordinary General Assembly of the Synod of Bishops, Sosa disagreed with the synod's description of secularization as "a dark phase that is in the process of being overcome", instead of calling secularization a "sign of the times" for the Catholic Church.

In February 2019, after guiding Jesuits and their lay collaborators through two years of discernment, Sosa announced four priorities that would guide the Society's decisions for the next decade. These were: teaching discernment through the use of the Spiritual Exercises, walking with the poor in their quest for dignity and justice, accompany young people in the creation of a hope-filled future, and collaborating in the care of our Common Home. Pope Francis declared these priorities to be very much in line with those of his pontificate.

His presence in the JDV campus has been a blessing to all of us, bringing us tremendous joy and enthusiasm. We hope that this issue of the Journal has been able to mediate that joy, which is characteristic of Arturo as well as the present Pope.

The AJRS team wishes each one of the readers a joy-filled and meaningful life.

The Editor